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“OF KINGS AND QUEENS”

What difference lies 'twixt thee and me?
If thou art King, then I am Queen;
If thou art peas, then I am beans—
Two humble forms, yet one same means.

For tell me, what is kingly might
Without a queen beside the light?
And what are peas when left alone,
Without their fellow fully grown?

We are but souls by Heaven wrought,
By the selfsame Maker shaped and taught;
Fashioned alike by God's own hand,
Upon the selfsame day we stand.

Thus boast not thine exalted name,
For flesh and spirit are the same;
No throne may stand by one alone—
For hearts are made as two, not one.